

Impact of Product, Process, Organisational, and Marketing Innovation on Micro, Small and Medium Scale Enterprises' Sustainability

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Abstract

Background: Rapid and efficient adoption of new business models is a key lever for improving an organisation's sustainable performance and one of the most important sources of enduring competitive edge. Nonetheless, studies show that a large number of business model innovations fail.

Objective: This study aimed to investigate how innovation, sustainability, and performance function as moderators in Micro, Small, and Medium-Scale Enterprises (MSMES).

Methodology: The study involved 100 culinary MSME actors from the twenty sub-districts of Bandar Lampung, Indonesia. To analyse the data and ascertain the correlation between variables, Smart PLS was utilised.

Results: Product, process, and organisational innovation have no impact on MSMEs' sustainability; according to statistical testing, only marketing innovation does. This suggests that the long-term survival of an MSME business, which is crucial in the culinary industry, is significantly impacted by marketing innovation. This study also reported that the performance of MSMEs has an impact on their sustainability. However, MSMEs' performance has no effect on the relationship between innovation of product, process, organisation, and marketing, and their sustainability.

Conclusion: Organisations, process, and product innovation have no bearing on the sustainability of MSMEs; only marketing innovation does. This demonstrates that the culinary industry values innovation in marketing, which makes a big difference in an MSME's long-term survival.

Unique Contribution: The study has provided empirical support for its practical implications, and the findings highlight areas of emphasis for improving the sustainability and innovation of MSMEs, two elements that appear to be essential for encouraging entrepreneurship and enhancing the financial circumstances of families with low incomes in developing countries, such as Indonesia, which are particularly vulnerable.

Key Recommendation: Innovation in marketing is a crucial component for businesses seeking to enhance their sustainability. It is suggested that businesses should strive to attain high innovation capabilities to achieve their goals.

Keywords: innovation; sustainability; performance; MSME; model

Introduction

Previous research has found that MSMEs, or micro, small, and medium-sized businesses, are extremely important to a nation's economy (Singh et al., 2023). MSMEs comprise approximately 90% of all businesses, generating 60% of employment and 50% of global GDP (Larios-Francia & Ferasso, 2023). MSMEs, on the other hand, continue to face a number of challenges, such as limited access to capital, inadequate infrastructure, constraints in product marketing and distribution, and the need for innovation, technology, and human resource development.

In addition, the MSME sector boosts entrepreneurship and innovation for the country's future expansion (Guleş et al., 2015). Furthermore, an innovation is a new or greatly enhanced process, marketing strategy, organisational technique, or product (good or service) that is introduced into a change in company operations, organisational layout, or relationships with the outside world (OECD, 2005). In today's socioeconomic environment, businesses must innovate to stay competitive, increase profits, and improve overall performance. Long-term business success has always required innovative thinking (Maier et al., 2020). The significance of innovation in

economic development is such that most people agree that the most crucial element is innovation, which influences company performance. Many businesses are attempting to boost profits through various forms or methods of innovation. Nonetheless, the body of research suggests that different innovative firms have different effects of innovation on business performance. Innovation has also been considered a crucial instrument for attaining sustainability (Adams et al., 2016). Furthermore, innovation and sustainability are critical links to advance economic, social, and sustainable development (Michelino et al., 2019).

Previous research found that innovation influences the performance of firms (Shouyu, 2017). Another study in Estonia examines the relationship between the financial performance of serial entrepreneurs' previous firms and the level of performance in their subsequent firms. This study's sample size was limited to firms that had survived four years. Good performance in previous firms is more durable than bad performance (Marmor & Lukason, 2024). Furthermore, previous research in Peru reported that process and organisational innovation had an impact on MSME performance, but product innovation had no effect (Larios-Francia & Ferasso, 2023).

Other research found that innovation in marketing has an impact on the sustainability of MSMEs (Affran et al., 2024; Horng et al., 2017; Na et al., 2019; Quaye & Mensah, 2019). It has been demonstrated that marketing innovation significantly and favourably affects family businesses' ability to survive. Technology resources have a significant negative mediating effect on the correlation between innovation of marketing and the sustainability of family businesses (Affran et al., 2024). Long-term competitive advantage was significantly impacted by the innovation of product and the innovation of communication in sharing economic businesses' marketing strategies. In addition, the long-term competitive advantage of sharing economy businesses had a profound effect on market dominance (Na et al., 2019). Additionally, other studies found that innovations in metal fabrication, fluid, drinks, and soaps all offer a long-term competitive edge through advancements in the design of goods and wrapping, advertisements, commerce, and price SMEs (Quaye & Mensah, 2019). In addition, another study found that sustainable innovation is more likely to be adopted when an organisation has a supportive environmental marketing strategy and culture. The study contributes significantly to the developmental domains of hotel sustainability and the spread of sustainable innovations (Horng et al., 2017). Furthermore, studies conducted in China have found that SMEs there only benefit from a mix of product-focused and production-oriented innovation, except if they also implement organisational shift at the same time (Zhang, 2022).

While a substantial number of previous studies have found how innovation in marketing has an impact on the sustainability of MSMEs, not much research has been devoted to examining how innovation, sustainability, and performance operate as moderators of MSMEs. The purpose of this study was to look into how innovation, sustainability, and performance function as moderators of MSMEs. In particular, this study would be an attempt to fill the gap in the literature related to both empirical and theoretical ways, as this study is relevant to entrepreneurial policymakers, creditors, government officials, and other stakeholders who work with serial entrepreneur-owned businesses.

Theoretical Background Innovation, Sustainability, and Performance

Innovation in business is unquestionably important because it can create something new, whether it is a product's appearance, system, or process. Changes in technology and the demands of consumers cause product tastes to shift over time. According to the Oslo Manual, innovation is a new or improved procedure or good that is made available to potential customers or adopted by the production unit and differs substantially from earlier iterations (OECD, 2005).

Product, process, marketing, and organisational innovation are the four main items of innovation. Innovation of a product is the introduction of a new or significantly improved good or service in terms of its characteristics or intended function. Furthermore, the innovation process utilises a new or significantly improved production or shipping method. Additionally, innovation in marketing involves adopting a new marketing strategy that comprises significant changes to the positioning, advertising, cost, or packaging of the product. Innovation of organisations involves adopting a new organisational strategy at work, in external interactions, or in the daily operations of the company (OECD, 2005). Another study found a strong relationship between business sustainability and innovative marketing. According to the findings, companies looking to improve their business sustainability must prioritise service and marketing innovation (Soomro, 2023).

Additionally, prior research found that the results of the Fuzzy WASPAS approach indicate that partnerships and collaboration, goods labelling, and environmentally friendly packaging are the most successful green innovation and marketing tactics. The results of this investigation can help the development of more successful environmental labelling initiatives and marketing strategies aimed at promoting sustainable consumption (Huang et al., 2024). Furthermore, data from developed nations show that businesses that implement several forms of innovation perform better than those that only implement one at a time (Zhang, 2022). However, in this term, we do not know whether the innovation conducted by MSMES in the culinary sector in Bandar Lampung has affected their sustainability.

Business sustainability is the process of integrating social, ecological, and economic aspects into an organisation's main commercial operations. It entails adopting practices that reduce negative environmental impacts while also improving social well-being and profitability. Businesses that embrace sustainability principles can gain a competitive advantage in an increasingly conscious market while also contributing to a more sustainable future. Sustainability, in its widest definition, is the capacity of a process to be sustained or upheld over an extended period of time. The goal of sustainability in business and policy is to keep natural or physical resources from being depleted so they can be used in the future (Maier et al., 2020). Therefore, businesses today must innovate in order to remain competitive, increase profits, and improve overall performance. It suggests that long-term business success has always necessitated innovative thinking. The application of sustainability innovations targeted at the mass market and benefiting the majority of society is basically what is meant by sustainable entrepreneurship.

On the other hand, firm performance is categorised into four categories: financial performance, innovative performance, productive performance, and market performance (Gunday et al., 2011).

In sum, businesses must innovate in today's socioeconomic environment to remain competitive, increase profits, and enhance overall performance (Larios-Francia & Ferasso, 2023; Listyaningsih et al., 2024). The importance of innovation in economic development is such that it is widely regarded as the most important factor influencing corporate performance. Many businesses are attempting to increase profits through a variety of innovative approaches. However, existing research suggests that the impact of innovation on company performance varies across many innovative firms. Furthermore, innovation is an important tool for achieving sustainability (Quaye & Mensah, 2019; Huang et al., 2024). Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) have advantages in terms of size, flexibility, risk-taking, and quick response to market changes. Pressures to innovate apply to both large and small firms, and several studies have found that SMEs' fertility, as well as comparative advantages in terms of innovation, are greater when compared to large companies. Furthermore, innovation can be divided into four categories: organisational, marketing, process, and product innovation (OECD, 2005). Previous research found that innovation influences MSMEs' performance (Larios-Francia & Ferasso, 2023). Furthermore, good performance in previous companies is more durable than poor performance (Marmor & Lukason, 2024). Thus, MSMEs' good or bad performance will have an impact on their long-term viability. As a result, MSME performance moderates the relationship between MSME innovation and sustainability. To the authors' knowledge, no prior research has been conducted to thoroughly investigate the relationship between innovation, sustainability, and performance as moderation in culinary MSMEs. That is what distinguishes the current study from previous ones. Given the preceding discussion, the following hypotheses are proposed to address the performance's critical moderating effect. Thus, the hypotheses are that:

H1: Innovation of the product affects sustainability positively

H2: Innovation of the process affects sustainability positively

H3: Innovation of the organisation affects sustainability positively

H4: Innovation in marketing affects sustainability positively

H5: Performance positively affects sustainability

H6: Performance moderates the relationship between innovation and sustainability

Methodology

This study employs two methodologies: descriptive and analytical. The descriptive method is used to describe the performance, sustainability, and innovation of culinary MSMEs as found through field research. The analytical method is used to explain observations arising from the relationship between variables, ultimately yielding new insights in the form of a model.

Participants in the research included culinary MSME actors from Bandar Lampung City's 20 sub-districts: East Tanjungkarang, Kemiling, West Tanjungkarang, Sukabumi, North Teluk Betung, Tanjung Senang, South Teluk Betung, Labuhan Ratu, Central Tanjungkarang, Way Halim, West Teluk Betung, Langkapura, Kedaton, Enggal, Panjang, Kedamaian, Sukarame, East Teluk Betung, Rajabasa, and Bumi Waras. The study's sample size was 100 MSME actors from 20 sub-districts in Bandar Lampung, which is considered adequate or representative.

To ascertain the correlation between the research variables, the data were subsequently analysed using a statistical programme known as Smart PLS. Smart structural equation modelling (SEM) based on partial least squares (PLS) has become a widely used statistical method. The proposed

relationships were tested first using the measurement model, followed by the structural model. The reliability and validity of the measurement model were assessed (Hair et al., 2022).

Next, the questionnaire's validity and reliability were assessed. The validity of a construct is evaluated by considering both its discriminant and convergent validity. When the average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct is 0.50 or greater and the outer loading of each item is greater than 0.50, convergent validity is supported (Hair et al., 2022). Furthermore, the composite reliability results are higher than the necessary 0.60 threshold (Henseler et al., 2009).

Results

Respondents' Background

The sample size for this study was 100 MSME actors drawn from 20 sub-districts in Bandar Lampung, which is considered adequate or representative. The majority of samples (48%) are under the age of 30, with 31% between the ages of 31 and 40. The third group is 41-50 years old (17%), followed by those over 50 (4%). 70% of the samples are highly educated, with 20% holding an undergraduate or postgraduate degree. Secondary education is ranked third with 6%, followed by basic education with 4%. Most samples have been in business for less than 5 years (63%), while those in second place have been in business for more than 6-10 years (33%), and those in fourth place have been in business for more than 11 years (4%). The majority of the samples have fewer than five people, more than 5-10 people, more than 10 people, and no workers, with 61%, 16%, 12%, and 11%, respectively. The majority of the samples' assets are less than or equal to IDR 50,000,000 by 69%, while those in second place are greater than or equal to IDR 50,000,000 - IDR 500,000,000 by 31%. The turnover of the majority of the samples is less than or equal to IDR 300,000,000 by 69%, while those in second place are more than or equal to IDR 300,000,000 - IDR 2,500,000,000 by 31%. Health insurance is rarely used (97%), with health insurance accounting for 3% of the total.

Partial Least Squares (PLS) analysis is a SEM (Structural Equation Modelling) method used to solve multiple regression problems such as missing values, small research sample sizes, and multicollinearity (Hair et al., 2014). Prior to conducting structural model analysis (inner model), a measurement model is required to test the validity and reliability of the indicators that comprise the latent construct. Convergent and discriminant validity are used to assess the measurement model (outer model). Validity testing determines whether research instruments can measure what should be measured. To ascertain whether measuring devices are consistent with a particular concept, the reliability test is utilised (Henseler et al., 2009). The following is a measurement model developed from the problem formulation:

Figure 1: Measurement Model. Source: own research

Validity Test

Assessing the model's validity is the next stage. Validity tests are classified into two types: convergent and discriminant. The outcomes of data processing using smartPLS software show that all indicators have outer loadings higher than 0.50. Convergent validity is thus demonstrated for constructs with indicators or outer model values.

Assessing discriminant validity can also be achieved by comparing each construct's root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) value to the correlation between the construct and the other constructs in the model. The following findings were obtained from the Convergent Validity-AVE test.

Table 1: Convergent Validity Test - AVE

Variables	Average variance extracted (AVE)	Results
Innovation of Organisation	0.700	Valid
Innovation of Product	0.638	Valid
Innovation of Process	0.686	Valid
Innovation of Marketing	0.658	Valid
Sustainability of MSMEs	0.664	Valid
Performance of MSMEs	0.697	Valid

Source: SmartPLS 4, 2024 data processing

Table 1 indicates that the latent variable already exhibits excellent discriminant validity, as its AVE value exceeds 0.50.

Reliability Test

=The internal consistency of the measuring device is evaluated using PLS's reliability test. The accuracy, consistency, and precision of a measuring device during measurement are referred to as reliability. The following output results were obtained from the test of reliability:

Table 2: Test of Reliability

Variables	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Results
Innovation of Organisation	0.783	0.875	Reliable
Innovation of Product	0.717	0.737	Reliable
Innovation of Process	0.766	0.723	Reliable
Innovation of Marketing	0.742	0.852	Reliable
Sustainability of MSMEs	0.762	0.775	Reliable
Performance of MSMEs	0.704	0.747	Reliable

Source: data processed by SmartPLS 4, 2024

It is clear from Table 2 that every variable is trustworthy. The high composite reliability and Cronbach's Alpha values, both of which are higher than 0.6, support this.

Structural Model (Inner Model)

Next, following data processing with the smartPLS 4.0 programme, the R-Square value is ascertained as follows:

Table 3: Test of R-Square

Variable	R-square adjusted	Result
Sustainability of MSMEs	0.652	Strong influence

Source: data processed by SmartPLS 4, 2024

The adjusted R-squared value of the MSME Sustainability variable, which was 0.652, is displayed in Table 3. These findings indicate that the innovation of the product can significantly influence the MSME Sustainability variable, encompassing innovation of the organisation, innovation of product, innovation of process, and innovation of marketing, all at the same time, by 65.2%, with other variables not included in the study's hypotheses accounting for the remaining 34.8%.

Hypothesis Testing

To ascertain whether there is a substantial correlation between research constructs, hypothesis testing is done. Values from the t-table are used in hypothesis testing, along with t-statistics produced by the smartPLS software's bootstrapping process. The outcomes of the bootstrapping process in this investigation are as follows:

Figure 2: Structural Model. Source: own research

Next, the t-statistic value, which is higher than the t-table value and shows a significant relationship between the research variables, can be used to illustrate hypothesis testing. A t-statistic value >1.96 in hypothesis testing denotes significant results, whereas a t-statistic value <1.96 denotes non-significant results (Henseler et al., 2009). The value in the path coefficient output for testing the structural model serves as the basis for hypothesis testing.

Path Coefficients

The next evaluation measurement is to test the Path Coefficient, which aims to identify if there is a positive or negative correlation between a variable and other variables. Using the smartPLS software's Bootstrapping process, testing at this point can be evaluated (Hair et al., 2014). According to the Path Coefficient test, a variable has a positive relationship direction with other variables if its value is greater than zero. Conversely, if the Path Coefficient is less than zero, the variable has a negative relationship with other variables.

Table 4: Path Coefficient Test Between Independent and Dependent Variables

Variables	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Organizational Innovation -> MSME Sustainability	1.118	0.263
Product Innovation -> MSME Sustainability	1.663	0.096
Process Innovation -> MSME Sustainability	0.144	0.885
Marketing Innovation -> MSME Sustainability	2.664	0.008
MSME Performance -> MSME Sustainability	3.512	0.000

Source: SmartPLS 4, 2024, processed the data

The hypothesis is supported by the data in Table 4, where each influence has a P-value <0.05. The dependent variable is thus significantly impacted by the independent variable. The following are the outcomes of the hypothesis test: Organisational innovation does not affect MSMEs' sustainability, according to the P-value (0.263>0.05); product innovation does not affect MSMEs' sustainability, according to the P-Value of 0.096 (>0.05); process innovation does not affect MSMEs' sustainability, according to the P-Value (0.885>0.05); innovation of marketing has a significant impact on MSMEs' sustainability, according to the P-Value (0.008<0.05); and, lastly, MSME performance has an effect on MSMEs' sustainability.

Moderation Effect Testing

The outcomes of bootstrapping hypothesis testing to ascertain the impact of moderation are as follows:

Table 5: Indirect Test

Variables	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
MSME Performance x Product Innovation -> MSME Sustainability	0.892	0.373
MSME Performance x Process Innovation -> MSME Sustainability	0.080	0.936
MSME Performance x Organisational Innovation -> MSME Sustainability	0.229	0.819
MSME Performance x Marketing Innovation -> MSME Sustainability	0.329	0.743

Source: own research

The conclusion can be drawn from the data presentation in Table 5 that there is no moderating effect of the moderating variable on the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The moderation test's findings are as follows: It is unacceptable to test the moderating effect of MSME performance on product innovation and MSME sustainability, as indicated by the P-values of 0.373>0.05. Testing the moderating effect of MSME performance on process innovation and MSME sustainability is unacceptable, according to P-Values of 0.936>0.05; testing the moderating effect of MSME performance on organisational innovation and MSME sustainability is unacceptable, according to P-Values of 0.819>0.05; testing the moderating effect of MSME performance on marketing innovation and MSME sustainability is unacceptable, according to P-Values of 0.743>0.05.

Discussion

Finding out how MSMEs in the culinary industry can maintain or enhance their competitive edge by incorporating particular resources and competencies is the aim of this paper. Previous research found that SMEs benefit from their size, flexibility, risk-taking, and ability to respond quickly to market changes (Larios-Francia & Ferasso, 2023). Statistical testing revealed that only marketing innovation has an impact on MSMEs' sustainability, whereas product, process, and organisational innovation have no effect. These suggest that marketing innovation is critical in the culinary industry and has a significant effect on the long-term viability of an MSME. During the COVID-19 era, online marketing was widely practised. It was an absolute necessity during social

restrictions, but it turned out that this created significant potential for changes in marketing MSME products, where previously marketing was not done online, was now done online (Quaye & Mensah, 2019; Huang et al., 2024). It has been proven that the presence of marketing innovation results in the sustainability of MSME businesses. The application of novel marketing techniques that call for significant modifications to the goods placement, promotion, cost, wrapping, or layout is known as innovation of marketing (OECD, 2005).

These findings support previous studies that have shown how the innovation of marketing influences the sustainability of MSMES (Affran et al., 2024; Na et al., 2019; Quaye & Mensah, 2019; Soomro, 2023). The marketing efforts of SMEs' owner-managers are concentrated on developing and or altering product designs and packaging, advertising strategies, pricing plans, and investigating streamlined and successful distribution networks (Quaye & Mensah, 2019). Another finding in this study was that the performance of MSMES influences their sustainability. However, MSMES' performance does not affect the relationship between innovation of product, innovation of process, innovation of organisation, and innovation of marketing and MSMES' sustainability (Shouyu, 2017). This indicates that MSMES have existed for at least four years, regardless of their performance, whether good or bad. This is among the conclusions drawn from the study.

In light of this study's findings, the majority of the surveyed samples consistently strive to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of their manufacturing processes, as well as to deliver the best service possible. In process innovation, it was found that the equipment used to produce products was not conventional. The majority of them used new business methods to communicate with third parties, according to organisational innovation research. In terms of marketing innovation, it was found that the majority of them had also run promotions on social media platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp, and TikTok, with products priced reasonably based on consumer preferences (Huang et al., 2024).

Conclusion

This study aims to investigate the connection between innovation, sustainability, and performance as moderators of MSMES in the culinary industry in Bandar Lampung, Indonesia. Statistical testing revealed that organisations, processes, and product innovation have no bearing on the sustainability of MSMEs; only marketing innovation does. This demonstrates that the culinary industry values innovation in marketing, which significantly impacts an MSME's long-term survival. Furthermore, this study found that MSMES' performance has an impact on their sustainability; however, the relationship between MSMES' sustainability and product, process, organisational, and marketing innovation remains unaffected by MSMES' performance. The results indicate that innovation in marketing is a crucial component for businesses seeking to enhance their sustainability.

Regarding the study's practical implications, the results highlight areas for enhancing the sustainability and innovation of MSMES, two factors that appear essential for encouraging entrepreneurship and improving the financial circumstances of extremely vulnerable low-income households in developing nations like Indonesia. The study's findings can be applied in other

developing countries where MSMEs account for the majority of firms and innovation significantly affects the sustainability and performance of businesses.

Limitations and Recommendations

The study's theoretical and managerial contributions are significant. However, some limitations could potentially lead to new research avenues for future researchers in the fields of performance, sustainability, and innovation in Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). To better understand how innovation affects sustainability and how innovation, performance, and sustainability are related, further research is required to analyse multi-source data from other MSMEs. Finally, because the sample was drawn from twenty sub-districts of one province's capital city in a developing country, the findings may be limited to a specific context; however, the same framework can be used in the future to conduct a cross-sectional study in other settings.

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References

- Adams, R., Jeanrenaud, S., Bessant, J., Denyer, D., & Overy, P. (2016). Sustainability-oriented Innovation: A Systematic Review. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 18(2), 180–205. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijmr.12068>
- Affran, S., Oppong, E. D. O., & Kolug, J. Y. (2024). Examining the moderating role of technological resources on marketing innovation and family business sustainability. *IIMBG Journal of Sustainable Business and Innovation*, 2(2), 143–162. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijsbi-01-2024-0003>
- Guleş, H. K., Zerenler, M., Cagliyan, V., Sener, T., & Karaboğa, K. (2015). The Effect of Market Orientation and Innovation Ability on Enterprise Performance: a Practice of Structural Equation Modelling Analysis: a Research on SMEs. *European Scientific Journal*, 1(May), 31–42.
- Gunday, G., Ulusoy, G., Kilic, K., & Alpkan, L. (2011). Effects of innovation types on firm performance. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 133(2), 662–676. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2011.05.014>
- Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., Hult, G. T., & Sarstedt, M. (2022). A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling. In *Sage*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2013.01.002>
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sinkovics, R. R. (2009). The use of partial least squares path modeling in international marketing. *Advances in International Marketing*, 20(2009), 277–319. [https://doi.org/10.1108/S1474-7979\(2009\)0000020014](https://doi.org/10.1108/S1474-7979(2009)0000020014)
- Hornig, J. S., Liu, C. H., Chou, S. F., Tsai, C. Y., & Chung, Y. C. (2017). From innovation to sustainability: Sustainability innovations of eco-friendly hotels in Taiwan. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 63, 44–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2017.02.005>
- Huang, L., Solangi, Y. A., Magazzino, C., & Solangi, S. A. (2024). Evaluating the efficiency of green innovation and marketing strategies for long-term sustainability in the context of Environmental labeling. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 450(March), 141870. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.141870>

- Larios-Francia, R. P., & Ferasso, M. (2023). The relationship between innovation and performance in MSMEs: The case of the wearing apparel sector in emerging countries. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 9(1), 100018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joitmc.2023.100018>
- Listyaningsih, E., Rahyono, R., Alansori, A., & Mukminin, A. (2024). Financial Literacy, Financial Inclusion, and Financial Statements on Msmes' Performance and Sustainability With Business Length As a Moderating Variable. *Ikonomicheski Izsledvania*, 33(1), 108–127.
- Maier, D., Maier, A., Aşchilean, I., Anastasiu, L., & Gavriş, O. (2020). The relationship between innovation and sustainability: A bibliometric review of the literature. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU12104083>
- Marmor, M., & Lukason, O. (2024). Financial performance persistence in serial entrepreneurship Financial performance persistence in serial entrepreneurship. *Cogent Business & Management*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2024.2423895>
- Michelino, F., Cammarano, A., Celone, A., & Caputo, M. (2019). The linkage between sustainability and innovation performance in IT hardware sector. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(16). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11164275>
- Na, Y. K., Kang, S., & Jeong, H. Y. (2019). The effect of market orientation on performance of sharing economy business: Focusing on marketing innovation and sustainable competitive advantage. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11030729>
- OECD. (2005). Oslo Manual-Guidelines For Collecting And Interpreting Innovation Data. In *Paris* (3rd editio). OECD. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315832685-107>
- Quaye, D., & Mensah, I. (2019). Marketing innovation and sustainable competitive advantage of manufacturing SMEs in Ghana. *Management Decision*, 57(7), 1535–1553. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-08-2017-0784>
- Shouyu, C. (2017). The Relationship between Innovation and Firm Performance: A Literature Review. *Proceedings of the 2017 7th International Conference on Social Network, Communication and Education (SNCE 2017)*, 82(Snce), 648–652. <https://doi.org/10.2991/snec-17.2017.132>
- Singh, A. N., Khanna, R., & Naidu, K. (2023). Role of MSME Sector in Growth and Development of the Economy: A Quantitative Investigation. *European Economic Letters*, 13(1), 350–354. <https://doi.org/10.52783/eel.v13i1.181>
- Soomro, M. A. (2023). Exploring Business Sustainability: Testing the Role of Service and Marketing Innovation. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 13(6), 2281–2298. <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v13-i6/17763>
- Zhang, H. (2022). Does combining different types of innovation always improve SME performance? An analysis of innovation complementarity. *Journal of Innovation and Knowledge*, 7(3), 100192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2022.100192>